

What's the Impact of Takeaway Management Zones?

Everyone deserves to live in an environment that enables them to thrive.

Healthy neighbourhoods help people make healthy choices to live well. Takeaway management zones are one way to achieve this.

NIHR-funded researchers sought to understand the impacts of takeaway management zones, reactions to them from takeaway businesses and their acceptability amongst members of the public.

Here's a summary of each of the 6 core papers produced.

RETAIL IMPACTS

Key Question

What is the impact of takeaway management zones on numbers of new takeaways?

Method

We used uncontrolled interrupted time series analysis to estimate changes from up to six years pre- and post-adoption of takeaway management zones around schools.

For **26** local authorities there was a **decrease** in the number of new takeaways within zones

12 (54%) fewer takeaways opened than anticipated after six years

Management zones **demonstrably curbed the proliferation of new takeaways.**

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HEALTH IMPACTS

Key Question

What are the health impacts of takeaway management zones?

Method

We used PRIMETIME, a proportional multistate lifetable model, and BMI change to estimate the impact of the intervention to 2040, in a closed-cohort of adults (25-64 years) in 6 local authorities across both urban and rural areas.

Relative to no intervention, we estimated a

reduction
in obesity prevalence in both sexes in all LAs*

*including by 2.3 percentage points and 1.5 percentage points in males living in Manchester and Wandsworth respectively, by 2040.

3 to 28

outlets per person reduction in takeaway exposure in Fenland (3) and Manchester (28), compared to no intervention, by 2031

This corresponded to per person reductions in BMI of

0.08

to to

0.68

kg/m², respectively

Reductions in incidence of disease including type 2 diabetes cases per 100,000 men:

964

FEWER

in Manchester by 2040

1206

FEWER

in Wandsworth by 2040

ECONOMIC IMPACTS

Key Question

What are the economic impacts of takeaway management zones?

Method

We projected the economic impacts of takeaway management zones to 2040 in three purposively selected local authorities using financial micro-data from the Annual Business Survey. We assessed the value of healthcare cost savings due to reductions in population overweight and obesity from reduced exposure to takeaways using the PRIMETIME model.

**£8.49m to
£12.78m
improvement**

in **Manchester** - the net economic impact associated with the adoption of takeaway management zones

**£4.67m to
£8.15m
improvement**

in **Sheffield** - the net economic impact associated with the adoption of takeaway management zones

Despite objections from industry, takeaway management zones are associated with **net economic benefits for local authorities, national government and the NHS.**

RETAILER OBJECTIONS

Key Question

How do takeaway businesses respond to takeaway management zones during local consultation?

Method

We identified and analysed objections to proposals submitted by or on behalf of food retailers in 41 local authorities.

Objections attempted to:

- determine other **causes** of poor diet and obesity
- suggest **alternative interventions**
- **undermine** evidence
- **influence perspectives** about local authorities and their intervention.

Objections consistently raised the same arguments but over time became less explicit and expressed a willingness to partner with local authorities to develop other solutions.

PUBLIC ACCEPTABILITY

Key Question

How does the public view takeaway management zones?

Method

We analysed data from the 2021 International Food Policy Study to investigate public acceptability of takeaway management zones.

Out of 3323 adults living in Great Britain:

50.8% supported zone adoption

37.3% were neutral

8.9% opposed

70.4% believed these zones would help young people to eat better

YOUNG PEOPLE'S PERSPECTIVES

Key Question

What are young people's perspectives on the acceptability of takeaway management zones?

Method

We recruited 46 young people aged 11-18 years attending secondary school within two takeaway management zones in London. Semi-structured, walking group interviews in the local food environment close to schools.

Young people find takeaway management zones **acceptable** and perceive them to have some **positive impacts**

But they did not see zones as being effective as they could be in limiting dietary risk - particularly in limiting a broader range of outlets selling unhealthy convenience food.

Our research has led to a toolkit for local authorities describing a **four step approach**

to the successful implementation of takeaway management zones.

The toolkit builds on our latest research, and explains how to adopt and implement evidence-based takeaway management zones in four steps, drawing on case studies, advice from those working in local authorities and examples of implementation processes.

Access toolkit

bit.ly/TMZ-toolkit

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